

**ANCILLARY FUNCTIONS AND TEACHING PERFORMANCE OF
SECONDARY PUBLIC-SCHOOL TEACHERS AT MAYAMOT
NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL: BASIS FOR INTERNAL
POLICY FORMULATION**

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Ancillary Functions and Teaching Performance of Secondary Public-School Teachers at Mayamot National High School: Basis for Internal Policy Formulation

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the ancillary functions and teaching performance of secondary public-school teachers at Mayamot National High School, District I-D, Division of Antipolo City during the School Year 2022-2023 which served as basis for school internal policy formulation. There were 20 teachers and 15 administrators that consisted of the school administrators, master teachers, and head teachers who answered the researcher-made questionnaire. It was revealed that both school administrators and the teachers themselves, perceived that the teachers are partly involved with grand weighted mean of 4.17 in handling the different ancillary functions such as grade level coordinators, coaches in academic and non-academic contests/sports, canteen managers, clinic teacher and other ancillary functions. Likewise, it showed that both the school administrators and teachers, despite the ancillaries assigned to them, they were still able to manage the challenges they encountered in performing their main function as teacher about instruction, material preparation, and time consciousness. Moreso, 50 percent of the teachers obtained an Outstanding, while the other 50 percent performed Very Satisfactory performance based on their IPCRF.

Keywords: *ancillary functions, teaching performance, secondary teachers*

Introduction

Everyone in the education system aspires to provide quality education. There are many factors affecting the quality of education, and as a teacher, the researcher has observed the prevalence of excessive tasks assigned to teachers apart from their primary teaching duties.

A sad reality in public school that the ancillaries are usually given to the newly hired teachers because they say it would serve as training ground for them. As experienced by the researcher, apart from five teaching loads with advisory class, she was given multiple ancillaries such as Information Communication Technology (ICT) Coordinator, Learner Information System (LIS) Coordinator, EBEIS Coordinator and Assistant Canteen Manager. Although the researcher was able to perform her main duties as a teacher and the tasks of the mentioned ancillaries, it was because she was single then and spent her weekends at school and brings home the unfinished tasks.

Also, to delegate the tasks equally among teachers to avoid staying late in school, going to school on weekends that supposed to be a time for family and so that the teachers would have a focus on the job of preparing lesson plan and other things related to teaching the students.

Teachers are often considered multi-taskers, believing that they can be more productive this way. However, the expert's opinion on productivity may have been considered. As Nathan Morris said, "It's not always that we need to do more, but rather that we need to focus on less" (Morris, 2019).

While multitasking has its advantages, such as finishing more tasks within an eight-hour workday and stimulating creativity (vii.works blog, 2022), it also has its drawbacks, including diminished focus and the potential for poorer work quality compared to those assigned to only one task.

The concerns of many teachers regarding the excess of ancillary tasks are reflective of a broader challenge in the education system. These educators often report difficulties focusing solely on teaching, as they are burdened with additional responsibilities like preparing lesson plans and meeting report deadlines for division offices. Such concerns have been consistently reported in the literature on educational practices and teacher workload.

In the school where the researcher was first assigned to teach, her colleague once questioned his role, pondering whether he was a teacher or an office staff member because of the paper works that to be prepared and submitted. The quality of education in public schools is perceived as inferior to that in private schools, with workload being a significant factor, as observed by many teachers. In Jun Rick Cano's Concept Paper on the "Factors Affecting the Deterioration of Educational System in the Philippines," he also highlights the pressure teachers face due to ancillary tasks (Cano, 2021).

As the saying goes that teaching is a noblest profession and it is a vocation that is why, even with so many workloads, the teacher would still perform his best in order to teach his students. Because at the end of the day, when you see the students that they learned something from you, you can say that it's all worth it. Molding their characters, shaping their minds and inspiring them to be successful individuals someday are priceless experience to a teacher.

These findings highlight the need for internal policy formulation in schools, particularly in secondary public schools like Mayamot National High School, to address the workload challenges faced by teachers. By focusing on these issues, schools can aim to improve the quality of teaching performance and ultimately enhance student learning outcomes.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the ancillary functions and teaching performance of secondary public-school teachers at Mayamot National High School, District I-D, Division of Antipolo City during the School Year 2022-2023 which served as basis for school internal policy formulation. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What was the extent of the secondary public school teachers' execution on ancillary functions designated to them as perceived by the school administrators and the teachers themselves on the following ancillary designation?
 - 1.1. Grade Level Coordinator
 - 1.2. Coaches in Academic and Non-academic contests/sports
 - 1.3. Canteen Manager
 - 1.4. Clinic Teacher
 - 1.5. and others indicated in the questionnaire
2. Was there a significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents on the ancillary functions of teachers in the aforementioned designation?
3. What were the specific challenges encountered by the secondary public-school teachers in performing their ancillary functions based on their primary duties as teacher listed below?
 - 3.1. Instruction
 - 3.2. Material Preparation
 - 3.3. Time Consciousness
4. What was the level of teaching performance of the teachers during the School Year 2022-2023 based on DepEd Evaluation Guidelines using IPCRF-Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF)?
5. Was there a significant relationship between the extent of the secondary public-school teachers on the ancillary functions and their teaching performance as perceived by the respondents?
6. What internal policy recommendations was proposed based on the findings of the study at Mayamot National High School?

Literature Review

Teachers always need a professional development for it is crucial for staying updated with the latest educational trends, methodologies, and technologies, as well as for enhancing teaching skills and knowledge. In the article of Margallo, Mabilangan, Llanes, (2019) titled, *Ancillary Assignments of Teachers: A Preparatory Professional Development Scheme for Teacher Leadership Enhancement*, it sought to determine if the ancillary tasks assigned to teachers will serve as a preparation for their professional development as leaders in the future.

The article "Unfolding Stories of English Teachers with Multiple Ancillary Functions in Maguindanao-1 Division" by Haron A. Mohamad and Marissa N. Parcon delves into the lived experiences of English teachers juggling multiple ancillary roles (Mohamad & Parcon, 2019). The study reveals a broad spectrum of additional responsibilities borne by teachers, from ICT coordination to being school program managers. While some teachers manage to balance these ancillary functions through various strategies, the teaching aspect often becomes deprioritized, resulting in inefficiencies and potential health issues. This study accentuates the tangible impact of ancillary functions on teaching performance, highlighting a critical area for policy attention (Mohamad & Parcon, 2019).

As stated from the article of Jomud et al. (2021) titled, *Teachers' Workload in Relation to Burnout and Work Performance*, teaching is a rewarding but demanding profession. Indeed, that teachers are prone to burnout due to long hours of teaching and a heavy workload.

In the study of Dr. Rosene D. Olaivar (2020) titled "Teachers' Attitude Towards Ancillary Functions in Relation to Job Commitment and Satisfaction, City Schools Division, Tagbilaran City, Bohol", The findings indicate a significant correlation between teachers' demographics and their attitudes towards ancillary functions, excluding teaching load. More critically, the research uncovers that a positive attitude towards ancillary functions correlates with higher job commitment and satisfaction, though the total number of ancillary functions does not predicate the teachers' attitudes towards them. This insight is crucial as it underscores the complexity of how ancillary functions influence teachers' professional lives, necessitating a policy response that acknowledges these nuanced relationships.

Sales et al. (2021) meticulously evaluated the classroom performance of secondary school teachers in the Third District of Bohol, utilizing both announced and unannounced classroom observations as key evaluation metrics. They establish a stark contrast between the performance in announced observations, deemed "Outstanding," and the "Satisfactory" rating in unannounced settings. This discrepancy highlights the need for a consistent and spontaneous evaluation mechanism, prompting Mayamot National High School to potentially standardize its evaluation practices and ensure a holistic and authentic assessment of teaching performance.

A reviewed study of Go and Valle (2023) titled, *Ancillary Functions, Self-Efficacy, and Resilience among Elementary School Teachers* discussed that teaching is regarded as the noblest profession, some of the teachers in public schools do not only play the roles of classroom related functions but are also tasked to perform various school related responsibilities or ancillary functions. Similarly, the study enumerated some of the ancillary functions that are being designated to teachers which are subject coordinators, grade level

chairpersons, organizations and club moderators, school paper advisers, coaches in academic and non-academic contests, canteen managers and members of various technical and working committee.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed the mixed method of research to gain a more complete data about the ancillary functions and teaching performance of secondary public-school teachers at Mayamot National High School.

According to Tegan George (2021), mixed methods research combines elements of quantitative research and qualitative research in order to answer the research question. To address the research issue, mixed methods research incorporates aspects of both qualitative and quantitative research. Because mixed techniques include the advantages of both quantitative and qualitative research, they can provide with a more comprehensive picture than either one alone.

Respondents

The sources of data being used in this study were the school administrators and teachers at Mayamot National High School located in Rose St., Greenheights Subdivision, Barangay Mayamot, City of Antipolo. School administrators include Master Teachers I-III, Head Teachers, and Department Teachers with a total number of 15. For teachers, this includes those who are handling ancillaries such as clinic teachers, canteen manager, grade level coordinators and coaches in academic and non-academic contests or sports with a total number of 20.

Instrument

The main instrument that was used to determine the level of teacher's teaching effectiveness in relation to ancillary work is a researcher-made questionnaire which composed of three parts. Part I are the list of ancillary functions that the respondent needs to select or check if which of those he/she was previously or currently assigned. Part II is a check box to identify if the respondent is teaching or non-teaching personnel. Part III are the challenges that the teachers encountered in terms of instruction, material preparation, and time consciousness.

Procedure

The researcher first submitted a request letter to the Division Office of Antipolo City asking permission to conduct the study at Mayamot National High School. After permission was granted by the Division Office, the researcher submitted an official letter to the principal of Mayamot National High school for the conduct of the study with the attachment of approved letter form the Division Office. Third, the researcher crafted a questionnaire to be used for data gathering. Fourth, the researcher submitted the questionnaire to the critic, adviser and statistician for checking, comments, and improvement of the questionnaire. After the approval was given by the adviser and critic, the researcher was advised to have the questionnaire be validated by five expert validators from the faculty of Marikina Polytechnic College. The researcher incorporated all the comments and suggestions of the expert validators for final printing of the questionnaires. After that, the researcher distributed the final copy of the questionnaires to the respondents and explained the data privacy act. The answered questionnaires were collected immediately.

The researcher ensured that the conduct of the activities relative thereto did not disrupt the classes nor used the prescribed working hours spent by the respondents. After the questionnaires were collected, the data was gathered, summarized and encoded. After that, the researcher consulted a statistician to analyze the data. The statistician advised the researcher to submit the first sample data gathered from the respondents to be used for pilot testing. After the research instrument passed the reliability test, collection of data was continued. Then, the complete data from the respondents was submitted to the statistician for analysis and for interpretation by the researcher based on the results.

Ethical Considerations

This study established ethical measures for the confidentiality of the information acquired from all the informants. It imposed neutrality with no manipulation of answers, and all responses were treated with the utmost confidentiality. Likewise, the privacy of the identities of the informants was sustained.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Extent of the Secondary Public-School Teachers' Execution on Ancillary Functions Designated to Them as Perceived by the School Administrators and the Teachers Themselves

The data imply that both school administrators and the teacher themselves, perceived that the Grade Level Coordinator completely attends all grade-level coordinatorship related meeting, checks school forms and prepares school reports related to learners, organizes grade-level activities to facilitate cohesiveness, coordinates the timely completion of required grade level tasks, and assists in the

evaluations, selection, distribution, and inventory of school supplies/materials.

Table 1. *Extent of the Secondary Public-School Teachers' Execution on Ancillary Functions Designated to Them as Perceived by the School Administrators and the Teachers Themselves in Terms of Grade Level Coordinator*

Grade Level Coordinator	Respondents			
	School Administrators		Teachers	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
1. Attends all grade-level coordinatorship related meetings	4.20	FI	4.00	PI
2. Checks school forms and prepares school reports related to learners	4.33	FI	4.40	FI
3. Organizes grade-level activities to facilitate cohesiveness	4.60	FI	4.27	FI
4. Coordinates the timely completion of required grade level tasks	4.47	FI	4.40	FI
5. Assists in the evaluations, selection, distribution, and inventory of school supplies/materials	4.13	PI	3.93	PI
Average Mean	4.35	FI	4.20	FI
Overall Average Mean	4.27 – Fully Involved			

This result is supported by the article “Unfolding Stories of English Teachers with Multiple Ancillary Functions in Maguindanao-1 Division” by Haron A. Mohamad and Marissa N.

Parcon that delves into the lived experiences of English teachers juggling multiple ancillary roles which revealed a broad spectrum of additional responsibilities borne by teachers, from ICT coordination to being school program managers. (Mohamad & Parcon, 2019).

Table 2. *Extent of the Secondary Public-School Teachers' Execution on Ancillary Functions Designated to Them as Perceived by the School Administrators and the Teachers Themselves in Terms of Coaching in Academic and Non-academic Contests/Sports*

Coaches in Academic and Non-academic Contests/Sports	Respondents			
	School Administrators		Teachers	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
1. Exercises parental authority and responsibility over the child while under their supervision, instruction, and custody.	4.27	FI	4.73	FI
2. Gives them support, advice, counsel companionship, and understanding.	4.60	FI	4.53	FI
3. Enhances, protects, preserves, and keeps them physically and mentally healthy at all times.	4.60	FI	4.47	FI
4. Represents them in all matters concerning their interests.	4.13	PI	4.13	PI
5. Train them in sports, academic or non-academic contests	4.00	PI	4.20	FI
Average Mean	4.32	FI	4.41	FI
Overall Average Mean	4.37 - Fully Involved			

The data suggest that both school administrators and the teacher themselves, perceived that the Coaches in Academic and Non-academic Contests/Sports completely exercises parental authority and responsibility over the child while under their supervision, instruction, and custody; gives them support, advice, counsel companionship, and understanding; enhances, protects, preserves, and keeps them physically and mentally healthy at all times; represents them in all matters concerning their interests, and train them in sports, academic or non-academic contests.

Teaching is her main function and shall not be neglected. As reiterated by the Department of Education (DepEd) on the DepEd Order No. 9, s. 2005 entitled “Instituting Measures to Increase Engaged Time-On-Task and Ensuring Compliance Therewith, classes shall not be disrupted.

Table 3. *Extent of the Secondary Public-School Teachers' Execution on Ancillary Functions Designated to Them as Perceived by the School Administrators and the Teachers Themselves in Terms of Canteen Manager*

Canteen Manager	Respondents			
	School Administrators		Teachers	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
1. Prepares the canteen report every month	4.27	FI	3.60	PI
2. Plans, organizes, and monitors the daily operations of the canteen	4.27	FI	3.47	PI
3. Provides leadership to the canteen employees and volunteers	4.13	PI	3.33	SI
4. Ensures the delivery of an affordable, healthy and safe food service to the community	4.13	PI	3.47	PI
5. Ensuring that students are treated with respect and dignity	4.47	FI	4.33	FI
Average Mean	4.25	FI	3.64	PI
Overall Average Mean	3.95 – Partially Involved			

The data imply that both school administrators and the teacher themselves, perceived that the Canteen Manager partly involves in preparing the canteen report every month, plans, in organizing, and monitoring the daily operations of the canteen, in providing leadership to the canteen employees and volunteers, in ensuring the delivery of an affordable, healthy and safe food service to the community, and in ensuring that students are treated with respect and dignity.

As stated from the article of Jomoad et al. (2021) titled, Teachers’ Workload in Relation to Burnout and Work Performance, teaching is a rewarding but demanding profession. It was cited from that workload has an impact on teachers’ performance as well.

Table 4. *Extent of the Secondary Public-School Teachers’ Execution on Ancillary Functions Designated to Them as Perceived by the School Administrators and the Teachers Themselves in Terms of Clinic Teacher*

Clinic Teacher	Respondents			
	School Administrators		Teachers	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
1. Provides basic health services and facilitates referral as needed	4.27	FI	3.93	PI
2. Provides health orientation to the school personnel	4.00	PI	3.80	PI
3. Plan annual health program and prepares consolidates health reports	3.80	PI	4.33	PI
4. Prepares and requests materials for the clinic and health programs	4.27	FI	3.47	PI
5. Coordinates with stakeholders	4.33	FI	3.87	PI
Average Mean	4.13	PI	3.88	PI
Overall Average Mean	4.01 – Partially Involved			

The data suggest that both school administrators and the teacher themselves, perceived that the Clinic Teacher partly involved in providing basic health services and facilitating referral as needed, in providing health orientation to the school personnel, in planning annual health program and in preparing consolidated health reports, in preparing and requesting materials for the clinic and health programs and in coordinating with stakeholders.

The DepEd Order No.002, Series of 2024, Immediate Removal of Administrative Tasks of Public School Teachers issued by the current Vice President also the Education Secretary Sara Duterte can attest on how school reports and school forms add burden to the teachers.

Table 5. *Extent of the Secondary Public-School Teachers’ Execution on Ancillary Functions Designated to Them as Perceived by the School Administrators and the Teachers Themselves in Terms of other Ancillary Functions*

Others	Respondents			
	School Administrators		Teachers	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
1. Manages parent consultation	4.67	FI	4.33	FI
2. Takes on classroom advisorship.	4.13	PI	4.80	FI
3. Takes charge of extra-curricular activities of the school	4.27	FI	4.27	FI
4. Takes on club advisorship/ moderatorship	4.33	FI	3.73	PI
5. Takes charge of parent-school linkages and activities.	4.20	FI	3.67	PI
6. Takes on inter-school activities as committee heads/members	4.53	FI	4.20	FI
7. Takes on co-curricular activities	4.27	FI	4.27	FI
8. Manages community involvement programs/activities of the school	4.67	FI	4.13	PI
9. Takes on subject coordinatorship	4.27	FI	4.27	FI
Average Mean	4.37	FI	4.19	PI
Overall Average Mean	4.28 - Fully Involved			

The data inferred that both school administrators and the teacher themselves, perceived that the teachers are completely involved in handling other ancillary tasks apart from the teaching functions such as parent consultation, classroom advisorship, extra-curricular activities of the school, club advisorship/ moderatorship, parent-school linkages and activities, committee heads/members of inter-school activities, co-curricular activities, community involvement programs/activities of the school and subject coordinator.

Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of The Two Groups of Respondents on Ancillary Functions of Teachers

Table 6. *Significant Difference between the Perceptions of the School Administrators and Teachers Themselves on Ancillary Functions of Teachers in terms of Grade Level Coordinator*

Respondents	Mean	p Value	Decision	Interpretation
School Administrators	4.35	0.96	Fail to reject Ho	Not Significant
Teachers	4.33			

There is no significant difference between the perceptions of school administrators and teachers in the implementation of ancillary functions of teachers in terms of Grade Level Coordinator. The data revealed that both school administrators and teachers have the

same views on the implementation of ancillary functions of teachers in terms of Grade Level Coordinator.

Table 7. Significant Difference between the Perceptions of the School Administrators and Teachers on Ancillary Functions of Teachers in terms of Coaching in Academic and Non-academic Contests/Sports

Respondents	Mean	p Value	Decision	Interpretation
School Administrators	4.32	0.56	Fail to reject Ho	Not Significant
Teachers	4.50			

There is no significant difference between the perceptions of school administrators and teachers in the implementation of ancillary functions of teachers in terms of Coaching in Academic and Non-academic Contests/Sports. The data showed that both school administrators and teachers have the same views on the implementation of ancillary functions of teachers in terms of Coaching in Academic and Non-academic Contests/Sports.

Table 8. Significant Difference between the Perceptions of the School Administrators and Teachers on Ancillary Functions of Teachers in terms of Canteen Manager

Respondents	Mean	p Value	Decision	Interpretation
School Administrators	4.25	0.27	Fail to reject Ho	Not Significant
Teachers	3.83			

There is no significant difference between the perceptions of school administrators and teachers in the implementation of ancillary functions of teachers in terms of managing the canteen. The data disclosed that both school administrators and teachers have the same views on the implementation of ancillary functions of teachers in terms of managing the canteen.

Table 9. Significant Difference between the Perceptions of the School Administrators and Teachers on Ancillary Functions of Teachers in terms of Clinic Teacher Ancillary

Respondents	Mean	p Value	Decision	Interpretation
School Administrators	4.13	0.61	Fail to reject Ho	Not Significant
Teachers	3.97			

There is no significant difference between the perceptions of school administrators and teachers on ancillary functions of teachers in terms of Clinic Teacher Ancillary. The data revealed that both school administrators and teachers have the same views on ancillary functions of teachers in terms of Clinic Teacher Ancillary.

Table 10. Significant Difference between the Perceptions of the School Administrators and Teachers on Ancillary Functions of Teachers in terms of Clinic Teacher Ancillary

Respondents	Mean	p Value	Decision	Interpretation
School Administrators	4.37	0.78	Fail to reject Ho	Not Significant
Teachers	4.30			

There is no significant difference between the perceptions of school heads and teachers on other ancillary functions. The data showed that both school administrators and teachers have the same views on other ancillary functions.

Challenges That the Secondary Public-School Teachers at Mayamot National High School Encountered in Performing Ancillary Functions Based on their Primary Duties as teacher such as Instruction, Material Preparation, and Time Consciousness

Table 11. Challenges That the Secondary Public-School Teachers at Mayamot National High School Encountered in Performing their Ancillary Functions Based on their Primary Duties in terms of Instruction

Instruction	Respondents			
	School Administrators		Teachers	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
1. The teacher did not meet the objectives of his/her lesson plan	2.20	D	1.87	D
2. The teacher did not utilize effective strategies to achieve maximum students participation	2.13	D	2.00	D
3. The teacher did not attain the target Mean Percentage Score (MPS) in periodical test	2.40	D	2.33	D
4. The teacher did not use the test result to improve his/her teaching performance	1.80	D	1.73	SD
5. The teacher did not conduct remediation or enhancement to the students in need	1.80	D	1.87	D
Average Mean	2.07	D	1.96	D
Overall Average Mean	2.01 – Disagree			

The data proved that both school administrators and the teacher themselves resist with the ideas that the teacher did not meet the objectives of his/her lesson plan, the teacher did not utilize effective strategies to achieve maximum students’ participation, the teacher did not attain the target MPS in periodical test, the teacher did not use the test result to improve his/her teaching performance, and that the teacher did not conduct remediation or enhancement to the students in need

Table 12. *Challenges That the Secondary Public-School Teachers at Mayamot National High School Encountered in Performing Their Ancillary Functions Based on their Primary Duties as teacher in terms of Material Preparation*

Material Preparation	Respondents			
	School Administrators		Teachers	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
1. The teacher did not prepare instructional materials (IMs) for the different classes he/she handles	1.73	SD	1.73	SD
2. The teacher did not prepare variety of IMs for the different lessons	1.73	SD	1.80	D
3. The teacher did not prepare a technology based instructional materials	1.73	SD	1.93	D
4. The teacher did not prepare IMs that is up to date	1.73	SD	1.87	D
5. The teacher did not prepare IMs that is engaging to the learners	1.73	SD	1.67	SD
Average Mean	1.73	SD	1.80	D
Overall Average Mean	1.77 –Disagree			

The data conclude that both school administrators and the teacher themselves resist with the ideas that the teacher did not prepare instructional materials (IMs) for the different classes he/she handles, the teacher did not prepare variety of IMs for the different lessons, the teacher did not prepare a technology based instructional materials, the teacher did not prepare IMs that is up to date, and that the teacher did not prepare IMs that is engaging to the learners.

Table 13. *Challenges That the Secondary Public-School Teachers at Mayamot National High School Encountered in Performing Their Ancillary Functions Based on their Primary Duties in terms of Time Consciousness*

Time Consciousness	Respondents			
	School Administrators		Teachers	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
1. The teacher was not present to his/her school	1.53	SD	1.53	SD
2. The teacher was not present to his/her class	1.53	SD	1.73	SD
3. The teacher did not submit lesson plan on a timely manner.	1.87	D	1.93	D
4. The teacher was not able to finish the competencies in the curriculum guide to be taught for every grading	1.73	SD	2.00	D
5. The teacher did not submit necessary reports on time	1.80	D	1.93	D
Average Mean	1.69	SD	1.83	D
Overall Average Mean	1.76 - Disagree			

The data imply that both school administrators and the teacher themselves resist with the ideas that the teacher was not present to his/her school, the teacher was not present to his/her class, the teacher did not submit lesson plan on a timely manner, the teacher was not able to finish the competencies in the curriculum guide to be taught for every grading and that the teacher did not submit necessary reports on time

Level of Teaching Performance of the Teachers During the School Year 2022-2023 Based on DepEd Evaluation Guidelines using IPCRF- Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form

Table 14. *Level of Teaching Performance of the Teachers During the School Year 2022-2023 Based on DepEd Evaluation Guidelines using IPCRF- Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form*

IPCRF Rating	Adjectival Rating	f	Percentage
4.50 – 5.00	Outstanding (O)	10	50%
3.50 – 4.49	Very Satisfactory (VS)	10	50%
2.50 – 3.49	Satisfactory (S)	0	0%
1.50 – 2.49	Unsatisfactory (U)	0	0%
Below 1.50	Poor (P)	0	0%
Total		20	100%

As shown in the table, the level of teaching performance of the teachers during the School Year 2022-2023 based on DepEd evaluation guidelines using IPCRF-Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form shows 50% or 10 out of 20 teachers rated 4.50 – 5.00 with adjectival rating Outstanding(O), and 50% or 10 out of 20 teachers rated 3.50 – 4.49 with adjectival rating Very Satisfactory (VS). The data proved that all teachers excellently performed their teaching functions and responsibilities.

Significant Relationship Between the Extent of The Secondary Public-School Teacher's on Ancillary Functions and Their Teaching Performance as Perceived by the Respondents

Table 15. *Significant Relationship Between the Extent of The Secondary Public-School Teacher's on Ancillary Functions and Their Teaching Performance as Perceived by the Respondents*

Ancillaries	R	Interpretation	p-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Grade Level Coordinatorship	-0.10	Negligible	0.69	Fail to reject H ₀	Not significant
Coaches in Academic and Non-Academic	-0.22	Weak	0.34	Fail to reject H ₀	Not significant
Canteen Manger	-0.04	Negligible	0.87	Fail to reject H ₀	Not significant
Clinic Teacher	0.01	Negligible	0.98	Fail to reject H ₀	Not significant
Others	0.08	Negligible	0.73	Fail to reject H ₀	Not significant

There was a weak correlation between the ancillary functions of teachers and teachers' performance as reflected in the computed r value -0.22. Moreover, since the computed p values of 0.69, 0.34, 0.87, 0.98, and 0.73 is greater than the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is confirmed. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between the ancillary functions and the teacher's performance.

The data imply that even the teachers are assigned with different ancillary functions, they can still manage to perform their main function as a teacher.

Internal Policy Recommendations Proposed by the Researcher Based on the Findings of the Study

Rationale

We often heard that teachers are good at multitasking. Yes indeed, this is true but we cannot deny the fact that in some ways, the main functions of a teacher such as preparing lesson plan, instructional materials and teaching the students are somehow being affected as revealed on the result of this study. As interpreted in Table 18, about the significant relationship between the extent of the secondary public school teacher's implementation of ancillary functions and their teaching performance as perceived by the respondents, there were negligible correlation between ancillary functions of teachers in terms of grade level coordinator, clinic teacher, and other ancillaries mentioned. Although it is a weak correlation, but it is revealed that somehow the main function is affected because of the ancillaries that the teacher needs to perform. According to Mark Anthony Llego an author of Teacher.ph DepEd public school teachers' claim that a heavy workload results to divided time and attention in the delivery of their core business which is teaching.

Republic Act no.4670, otherwise known as the "Magna Carta for Public School Teachers," provides that teaching hours for teachers shall not be more than six hours. This is implemented already by the school heads to their respective schools. Teachers are given five loads (plus advisory class considered as one teaching load) or six loads of actual teaching hours, and other 2 hours or more are spent in material preparation, lesson planning, and other related tasks. However, the two-hour time remaining for material preparation, lesson planning, recording outputs, etc. plus the ancillaries assigned to the teachers are not actually enough to finish all of it that is why, teachers are bringing home the unfinished tasks in order to fulfill his duties and responsibilities. As a result, the teacher sacrifices his time for his family. In this regard, the researcher formulated this policy.

Objectives

This formulated internal policy can be implemented all year round, that aims to achieve the following:

For the teachers to be able to lessen the burden of too much workload.

For the teachers to be able to avoid bringing home the unfinished such as class records, lesson plan, instructional materials, school forms and other teacher related tasks.

For the teachers to be able to focus on teaching the students.

For the students and teachers to receive a quality of health service from school clinic staff.

For the students and teachers to enjoy a variety and healthy food being sold at the school canteen.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following are the conclusions drawn from the results of the study.

It can be concluded that the present study together with other related studies cited here are evidence that the public school teachers have predicaments about their work load and ancillaries that needs to be addressed by the school administrators and the Department of Education that is why DepEd Secretary Sara Duterte issued a recent memorandum about DepEd Order No.002, S.2024 (Immediate Removal of Administrative Tasks of Public School Teachers).

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that even though teachers of Mayamot National High School feel burdened of the teaching loads and ancillaries, they can still cope with all the challenges and work pressure they experience. The have strong

commitment to their profession, they enjoy working because of the help and support of their colleagues and they are satisfied with their job as teacher.

In general, based on the findings of the study, the ancillary functions developed them to become resilient public servants.

References

DepEd Order No. 9, s. 2005 Instituting Measures to Increase Engaged Time-On-Task and Ensuring Compliance Therewith. Retrieved May 8, 2024, from <https://www.teacherph.com/reiterating-no-09-s-2005-instituting-measures-increase-engaged-time-task/>.

DepEd No. 002, Series of 2024. Immediate Removal of Administrative Tasks of Public School Teachers. Retrieved April 26, 2024 from https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/DO_s2024_002.pdf

George T. (2021) Mixed Methods Research | Definition, Guide & Examples. Retrieved May 14, 2024, from <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/mixed-methods-research/>.

Mohamad, H. A., & Parcon, M. N. (2019). Unfolding Stories of English Teachers with Multiple Ancillary Functions in Maguindanao-1 Division: A Phenomenological Study. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*.

Olaivar, R. D. (2020). Teachers' Attitude Towards Ancillary Functions in Relation to Job Commitment and Satisfaction, City Schools Division, Tagbilaran City, Bohol.

Sales, E. L., Belgira, K., & Salise, S. (2021). Classroom Performance and Ancillary Functions Among Secondary School Teachers in the Third District of Bohol. *University of Bohol Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(1), 57-85. <https://doi.org/10.15631/ub.mrj.v9i1.133>.

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